

The Influence of Internally Generated Revenue on Revenue Profile of Osun State: A Study of Ilesha West Local Government Area

Adewale Akanni ADEDAPO

&

Modupe Oluremi ALBERT

Dept. of Politics and International Relations

Lead City University, Ibadan

Abstract

In Nigeria, inadequate revenue and constrained fiscal jurisdiction have distanced local administrations from the populace to the point where, despite the enormous potential for growth they hold, people are now doubtful of the local government leadership significance. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate internally generated revenue on revenue profile of Osun State in Ilesha West Local Government Area. The study was premised on the devolution theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and ex post facto research design. The population of the study included all revenue generating profile of Ilesha West Local Government Area, Osun State, and copies of questionnaire were distributed for the collection of data. The sample size for the study was 170 and the sampling technique adopted was the purposive sampling technique. The study concluded that there is the need for management and organizational approach that emphasizes services, support and information for the honest tax payers. Increase tax revenue is a function of effective enforcement strategy which is the pure responsibility of tax administrators. The study recommended that there should be sufficient fund by government and non-government organizations. Local government should equally diversify, and strengthen her internally generated revenue base through tax, levies, rates and other charges. There should also be an avoidance of using IGR for political patronage.

Keywords: Internally generated revenue, Local government, Nigeria

Introduction

In Nigeria, fiscal federalism has resulted in the duplication of governmental duties and the misappropriation of public monies. The 1976 Guidelines for Local Government Reforms established local government as a subnational level of the federal framework. 774 local governments in Nigeria have been given duties and powers by the constitution (Osisioma, & Chukwuemeka, 2007).

Nigerian LGAs are obligated to fulfil certain duties, despite the financial crisis and difficulties they encounter in raising the funds needed for their approved budgets (Osisioma, & Chukwuemeka, 2007). The expansion of natural resources other than mineral extraction and agriculture; delivery and upkeep of healthcare services; and additional obligations that may be delegated to a local government council by the state's House of Assembly (Morufu, Oladejo, & Babatope, 2017).

In Nigeria, inadequate revenue and constrained fiscal jurisdiction have distanced local administrations from the populace to the point where, despite the enormous potential for growth they hold, people now doubt the significance of local government leadership. The willful tax avoidance by citizens caused by the ruling class lack of accountability and transparency is a factor in the difficulties local administrations face (Odupitan, 2017). One of the issues preventing the efficient operation of local governments in Nigeria has been recognized as the arbitrary formation of unprofitable local governments. Some locations where local governments exist lack the local economy needed to support the administration. They should be a part of a more effective local administration, which when combined with other factors will accelerate sociopolitical development (Ibrahim & Adamu, 2017).

Many local governments lack the professional employees needed to carry out their obligations because they lack the human capability to carry out their statutory and shared responsibilities. People who lack the necessary administrative and leadership abilities to bring the benefits of government to the people are hired because of their connections, family ties, and capacity for bribery (Ibrahim & Adamu, 2017). Inefficiency and low production are frequently the results of this issue, which is compounded by employee indiscipline and a shortage of working materials. Nigerian leaders also lack consistency due to frequent changes of policies and organizational structures and consecutive governments. When a new administration emerges in Nigeria, it is customary for people to disregard or forget about it. They then begin new programs that may or may not be completed before the end of the tenure and such incentives will also be abandoned by the next administration after them. This leads to a challenge that affects the efficiency or effectiveness of Local Governance in Nigeria.

One of the issues with effective tax payment in Nigerian local government administrations continues to be the lack of adequate information about taxpayers. In Nigeria, taxpayers can simply avoid informing the state or local government of their income. Because the administrations are constantly short on money, their capacity to perform their leadership duties is being negatively impacted by the taxpayers' lack of cooperation. Many Nigerian taxpayers do not view paying taxes as a civic duty and a duty to the government (Dennis & Emmanue, 2014). This is due to their perception that the government is not adequately providing the public goods and services that the people depend on as a result of paying taxes.

An issue with local governments' capacity to create impressive internal revenue is the incompetence of tax inspectors. Most tax officers lack the necessary training and interpersonal abilities. They are not motivated to make payments on time or honestly because of how uncivilised they interact with citizens or tax payers. They approach their work with aggression and self-interest, allowing a taxpayer the chance to defend his civic duty (Ilemona, Nwite & Oyedokun, 2019).

The central focus of this study is to find out of the most productive sources of Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) of Ilesa West Local Government Area Osun State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this research are to:

1. investigate how Internal Generated Revenue influence the finances of Ilesa West Local Government Area, Osun State; and

2. examine the impact of Internal Generated Revenue on the level of infrastructural development in Ilesa West Local Government Area, Osun State.

Literature Review

The Concept of Local Government

The local government system was introduced as the government of the people for grass root development. The indirect rule system, was introduced by Lord Lugard, established guidelines for local government reforms in 1990. The term 'local government' in a unitary state means the organ which, though completely subordinate to the central legislature, is independent of the central executive in appointment, and, to some extent, in its decisions and exercise a partially independent control over certain parts of public finance. The term 'local government' is applied to those organs which exist at the will of the central government, and which, while they exist, have certain definite powers of making regulations, controlling certain parts of public finance, and executing their own laws or the laws of the central legislature, over a given area (Abba, Bello & Hassan, 2018).

The government of the people and by the people, as visualized by Lincoln is obviously not possible in the modern nation states. It existed in ancient Greek city - states where people used to govern themselves due to smallness of area and population. In modern states, it is not possible for entire population to have a direct share in the government. In such situation, the national or central governments have created small self-governing units at the local level where the representatives of the people can sit to settle their problems and suggest measures for the welfare and development of the local areas. These small self-governing units, viewed together, form the local government in the country (Adams, 2015). So, the local government in modern times is a combination of small self-governing non-sovereign units with maximum authority devolved on them by the central government to manage the local affairs with local resources without any interference from the center.

John Clarke, in his book titled; "Outlines of the Local Government," defined local government as that part of the government of a nation which deals mainly with such matters as concern the inhabitants of a particular district or place and which it is thought desirable should be administered by local authority subordinate to the central government (Clarke, 1939).

Local government in any country is needed, as it is impossible for a single authority directly to undertake the performance of all those duties adequately, effectively and efficiently. In fact, the central government has neither the time nor the requisite knowledge of all the diverse problems, which are peculiar to different areas (Adebayo, 2018). According to some scholars, there cannot be full benefit of democratic government, unless we begin by the admission that all problems are not central problems and that the result of problems in their incidence requires decision at the place, and by the persons, where and by whom the incidence is most deeply felt. This constitutes the real problem of local government and from this emerges the need for decentralization.

Local Government Internally Generated Revenue

The term 'IGR' originated in the 1930s and evolved to encompass several facets of governance that are different from, but supplementary to federalism. Among the features of IGR that set it apart from federalism are: prominence of policy (rather than mainly legal) issues; inclusion of all governmental entities local units in addition to national-state (federal) relations; importance of official attitudes (perspectives) and actions; regular, continuous day-to-day interactions among officials; and inclusion of all types of public officials – especially administrators in addition to elected officials (Sundquist, 1969).

IGR includes as proper objects or study all the permutations and combinations of relations among the units of government. "It is human beings clothed with office who are the real determiners of what the relations between units of government will be". He asserted that, individual interactions among public officials is at the core of IGR. In this sense, it could be argued that federalism deals with the anatomy of the system, whereas IGR treats its physiology. Although, unitary forms of government allow for little or no semi-autonomous local units of government, IGR is not restricted to only federal system, and therefore, not a substitute to federalism. Wright goes on to argue that IGR is the continuous day-to-day pattern of contacts, knowledge, and evaluations of government officials (United Nations, 1965). A major concern is with the informal as well as with the formal, the practices as well as the principles, pursued in both competitive and cooperative inter-jurisdictional patterns a reminder of the formal, legal, institutional context within which those relationships originate and flourish. IGR refers to a significant domain of political, policy and administrative actions by public officials. It involves integration of resources and joint use of power in a mutual effort to resolve the nation's social and economic challenges. It has also to do with the leverage which each government is able to exercise on other governments in influencing the design and delivery of government programmes and services (Sundquist, 1969).

To begin with, concept explication and clarification have their uses; but they also have limits. There is much more to be said about the realities, practices and problems of IGR. This is an era when the management of IGR is a matter of major moment. It was observed that "The federal system is too important to be left to chance". His book can be seen as an effort to critique and reconstruct the organisational philosophy undergirding effective IGR action. In line with Sundquist's treatment, the mood of this paper moves toward a similar conclusion that IGR achievements hinge on coping successfully with complexity (United States Advisory Commission on Intergovernmental Relations, 1980). Thus, complexity is an inherent and persistent characteristic of the several features of IGR. An intrinsic linkage between decentralisation and IGR is that accomplishments in IGR arena depend on the successful management of complexity – hence the need for decentralisation.

Thus, decentralisation is a way of managing IGR in order to make it more efficient and effective. As the nation grew, it becomes apparent that not all decisions could be made at the top. Rapid increases in organisational size and complexity resulted not only in decentralisation, but also in an emphasis on both the line item budget to ensure accountability and the position classifications and

elaborate task descriptions to improve the manager's capacity to control the organisation⁹⁴. We have had a state-centred variety of IGR, arising from the need of the central government to rely on the states as its primary implementing agents and to achieve state cooperation if almost any of its functions were to be discharged successfully decentralisation serves this purpose.

Empirical Review

Banabo and Koroye (2015) studied stimulating internally generated revenue in Nigeria. The empirical study of literature is an interdisciplinary field of research which includes; psychology, sociology, philosophy, the contextual study of literature, and the history of reading literary texts. As a way of gaining knowledge by means of direct and indirect observation or experience, empiricism would be highlighted in this study by establishing some features and empiricism values some research more than other kinds. Empirical evidence (the record of one's direct observations or experiences) can be analyzed quantitatively or qualitatively. A plethora of empirical studies have been carried out on public revenues and expenditure without given much attention to the linkage between internally generated revenues and capital votes utilization mostly at the sub-national levels. In an investigation of the interrelationship between total government expenditure and total tax revenue in Barbados, it was revealed from the empirical findings that a unidirectional causality exists from tax revenue to government expenditure.

Tapang, Onodi & Amaraihu (2018) conducted a study on the effect of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in the petroleum industry in Nigeria. The findings revealed that tax incentives proxy by investment tax allowance, non-productive rent, capital allowance has a significant effect on foreign direct investment. Based on the findings it is concluded that firms' enjoying tax incentives will generate more employment opportunities than firms in highly taxed regions. Conducive investment climate is a strong requirement for the flow of sustainable physical investment in an economy. Tax incentives positively influences the living standards and per capital income, and expand variety of goods available to consumers. The limitation to this study was the fact that the study focused on foreign direct investment.

Ilemona, Nwite and Oyedokun (2019) studied the effects of multiple taxation on the growth of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. They discovered that multiple taxes have negatively affected the growth of SMEs in Nigeria as many operators of these businesses expressed their unwillingness to venture into new enterprises or expand the existing ones for fear of multiple taxes that continue to take a significant portion of their earnings.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted the devolution theory. There are often grassroots demands to achieve democratic ideals. Some movements are designed to contain or to appease centrifugal forces, ethnic conflicts, and/or separatism, and to diffuse social and political tensions by allowing local cultural and political autonomy. There may even be some political opportunism using decentralization for electoral

objectives and/or just a desire to not be left behind in this popular form of institutional reform. Devolution is a process in which the central government of a given country grants powers to sub-national governments (e.g. regional, state, or local governments). This process of decentralization distributes power to territories that want more authority over their own affairs. An accepted example of devolution is the United Kingdom. Usually, the central government maintains power of things like national security and defense but allows devolved governments to do things like set up courts, make laws, and regulate education⁵⁰.

Devolution is very similar to fiscal federalism. In the U.S. federal system of government, state governments have the power to make their own laws and policies. The Federal government is sovereign and maintains powers over foreign policy, political economy, defense and similar duties, but each state and municipal administration can govern itself.

Devolution describes the transfer of authority from a senior level of government to a junior level, and can be viewed as both a theoretical concept and as an administrative process. Theoretically, devolution can be seen as an instance of decolonization which can be usefully related to literature on political development. As an administrative process, the study of devolution can contribute to understandings of institutional change in general, and also to particular issues of development administration...”

There are two dimensions to the concept: Decentralization (devolution) has a spatial aspect in that authority and responsibility are moved to organizations and jurisdictions in different physical locations, from the center to the local level. And it has an institutional aspect in that these transfers involve reallocating roles and functions both within government, from one central government agency to lower-level jurisdictions and agencies; and between government and civil society, through service coproduction and partnerships as well as joint policymaking and feedback mechanisms (Anyebe, 2017).

Arguments favouring the devolution of powers and resources to local levels of governance emphasize that the enhanced decision-making power, authority and control over resources play a pivotal role economic and social development. They contend that devolution will result in increased citizen participation in local political processes where “local governments are perceived to have the capacity to make political and financial decisions affecting their economic and social welfare”. The improved allocation of resources is the most common theoretical argument for. It is argued that by bringing government closer to local people, the government will be better informed about local needs and preferences. This, as argued will result in increased accountability and enhanced responsiveness of government officials at the local or regional levels of government (Abubakar, 2017).

Local government as the third tier of government debatably, is purposefully established to promote development owing to its closeness to the people at grass roots level, therefore, enhancing its ability to easily articulate and aggregate socio-political and economic demands of the people.

Sorka argues that local government means the decentralization of authoritative decision

making where by the authority to make decision is displaced downwards from remote points near the top administration or outward from geographical locations, thus bringing authority closer to the people affected by it. Wraith closely argued that local government is a the act of decentralizing socio-political and economic power, which may take the form of devolution. In this perspective, it was opined by Oyediran that local government is the diffusion of political process on area basis (Osakede, Ijimakinwa & Adesanya, 2017).

However, perceived local government as a system of local administration under local communities organized to maintain law and order, provide some limited variety of social amenities, while encouraging formal organizational and democratic framework which enables the locals to conduct their affairs effectively for their general good or development (Abubakar, 2017).

A local government system is expected to enjoy autonomy, separate legal identity, territory, population, localness, democratic representation, specificity of powers delegated from the central government, and uniformity of structure. As a system of local administration under which local communities and towns are organized to maintain law and order the local administration must provide some limited range of social services and public amenities, and encourage the cooperation and participation of the inhabitants in joint endeavors towards the improvement of their conditions of living (Osakede, & Ijimakinwa, 2014). It provides the grassroots communities with a formal organizational framework which enables them to conduct their affairs effectively and also regulate the actions of their members for national good.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design and ex post facto research design. The population of the study included all revenue generating profile of Ilesha West local government area, Osun State, 5 top executives in Ministry of Finance, Osun State, Monthly Statutory Allocation Document, Osun State by the Federal Bureau of Statistics. Questionnaire was distributed for the collection of data. The sample size for the study was 170, while the sampling technique adopted was the purposive sampling technique.

Table 1: Demographic Data**Presentation of Data**

Variables	Categories	(Freq)	(%)
Gender	Male	103	60.6
	Female	67	39.4
	Total	170	100
Religion	Christianity	115	67.6
	Islam	52	27.1
	African Traditional	3	1.8
	Total	170	100
Educational Qualification	WASSC/NECO	30	17.6
	OND/NCE	48	27.1
	HND/B.sc	78	45.9
	M.sc/MA/MPA/PhD	16	9.4
	Total	170	100
Staff Status	Senior Staff	122	71.8
	Management Staff	48	28.2
	Total	170	100
	Ilesha West	170	100
	Total	170	100
Ministry/Agency	Ministry of Finance	53	31.2
	Ministry of Health	2	1.2
	Ministry of Education	8	4.7
	Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Matters	45	26.5
	Missing Value	62	36.5
	Total	170	100
Local Government Council	Ilesha West	62	36.5
	Ife East	20	11.8
		25	14.7
	Missing Value	63	37.1
	Total	170	100

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2022

Table 1 revealed that the number of male respondents amount to 103 respondents, which is 60.6% of the sample size of 170, while the female respondents amount to 67 respondents, which is 39.4% of the total sample size. The religion background of the respondents, being gathered revealed that three major religions are involved, which are Christianity, Islam and African traditional religion. The Christians are the most populated religion with 115 respondents, which amount to 67.6% of the sampled size, the Muslim were 52 which is 30.6% of the sample size, and the African traditional religion are the least respondents with 3 people, amountng to 1.8% of the sample size.

Educational Qualification is another variable in the socio-demographic data as presented by the table above. It shows that only 30 respondents are with West African Senior School Certificate (WASSC)/ National Examination Council (NECO) qualification which amount to 17.6% of the sample size, and 48 respondents, which is 27.1% of the sample size, have Ordinary National Diploma (OND)/ National Council Examination (NCE). While 78 respondents, which are 45.9% of the sample size, have Higher National Diploma (HND)/ Bachelor of Science (B.sc) qualification, 16 other respondents, which are 9.4% of the sample size, have M.sc/MA/MPA/Ph.D qualifications. In this variable, while those holding HND/B.sc qualification are the most populated of the sample, those with M.sc/MA/MPA/Ph.D qualification are the least populated. The analysis of the next variable on table, which is the staff status, indicates that there are 122 senior staff, which is approximately 71.8% of the sample size, and 48 management staff, which amount to 28.2% of the sample size. However, the senior staff is the most populated and the Management staff is the least populated.

The duty post of the respondents in Western States of Nigeria shows that there are 51 respondents working in Lagos State, which amount to 30% of the total sample size, 71 respondents are situated in Oyo State, amounting to 41.8% of the total sample size and 48 respondents, which is 28.2% of the sample size, are working in Osun State. The next variable and the eighth, on the socio-demographic table are the various Ministries/Agency represented by various respondents. There are 53 respondents from the Ministry of Finance, which amount to 31.2% of the sample size, 2 respondents from the Ministry of Health, which is 1.2% of the sample size, 8 respondents from the Ministry of Education, which is 4.7% of the sample size, 45 respondents from the Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affair, which amount to 26.5% of the sampled size. The missing value from this variable is 62 amounting to 36.5% of the sample size.

The local government council in which the respondents are working was also analysed Ilesha West has 20 respondents, equivalent to 11.8% of the sample size. The missing value is 63 amounting to 37.1% of the sample size.

The next variable and the tenth, is the Department or Unit of the respondents. Here we have 59 staff, which is 34.7% of the respondents in the Account and Finance department, while 27 staff, which is 15.9% of the respondents is from Administrative department. Meanwhile, 34 staff, which is 20% of respondents, is from the Audit department, 24 staff, amounting to 14.1% of the respondents, is from Education department, and 26 staff in other departments.

Presentation of Research Questions

Research Question 1: How has IGR influence the finances of Ilesa West Local Government Area of Osun State?

Table 2: Efficiency and Effectiveness IGR and Finances of Ilesha West Local Government Area, Osun State

Variables	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neither Agree nor Disagree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total	
	(Freq)	(%)	(Freq)	(%)	(Freq)	(%)	(Freq)	(%)	(Freq)	(%)	(Freq)	(%)
Reduced wasteful spending and corruption in the local government	70	41.2	53	31.2	14	8.2	19	11.2	14	8.2	170	100
Resulted in effective monitoring of local government expenditure	51	30.0	69	40.6	12	7.1	27	15.9	11	6.5	170	100
Led to reduction in Mismanagement and corruption at local govt	58	34.1	56	32.9	20	11.8	21	12.4	15	8.8	170	100
Led to transparency and accountability in the activities of the state and local government	55	32.4	56	32.9	31	18.2	18	10.6	10	5.9	170	100
Disbursement of funds from this account is highly efficient and transparent	55	32.4	52	30.6	22	12.9	23	13.5	18	10.6	170	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2021.

State Local Government Joint Account has led to transparency and accountability in the activities of the State and Local Government in the South Western Nigeria, while 16.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement and 18.2% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the statement.

Lastly, 63% of the respondents agreed that disbursement of funds from the State Local Government Joint Account is highly efficient and transparent, while 24.1% disagreed with the I statement and 12.9% neither agree nor disagree with the statement.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of Internal Generated Revenue on the level of infrastructural development of Ilesha West Local Government Areas of Osun State?

Table 3: Showing Indicators of IGR's intervention on Infrastructural Development in Ilesha West, Osun State

Infrastructural Development Indicators	2018 (% IGR)	2019 (% IGR)	2020 (% IGR)	2021 (% IGR)
Universal Basic Education	13.98%	12.72%	11%	13.27%
Road Construction & Repair	18.7%	16.5%	16%	15.58%
Rural Agriculture	5.05%	5%	5%	5.08%
Primary Healthcare	6.95%	8.75%	10%	7.16%

Source: field survey, 2022

Table 4: Osun State Universal Basic Education Board Projects' Implementation 2018 to 2020

Year	Name of Project	Project Description	Implementation Agency	Cost(N)
2018	Construction	Construction of eight 1000-Capacity Model Middle school with all facilities	UBEC/SUBEB	1,309,295,975
2019	Construction	Construction of eleven 900 Capacity Model primary school	UBEC/SUBEB	1322128317
2020	Construction	Construction of 154 Model classroomms Block	UBEC/SUBEB	677924955

Human capital development is vital for the progress and sustainable development of any nation. In such a case, the quality of input depends on the level of literacy of the population, which would help in the rapid social and economic development of a nation (Ajiye, 2014). In order to achieve this objective, the Nigerian government introduced Universal Primary Education (UPE) programme, aimed at eradicating illiteracy, ignorance, and poverty. therefore, stimulating and accelerating national development.

Therefore, the data on table 4 above revealed various indicators of IGR's intervention on Infrastructural Development in Ilesha West, Osun State. While table 3 specifically shows various construction and rehabilitation projects as well as instructional materials, individually or jointly provided by UBEC. Although, there was a flow of counterpart fund from the federal government to the state government between 2010 and 2017 for the implementation of the SUBEB projects, yet, the data showed that instructional and learning materials were relatively very small considering the pupils' enrollment in the state. The various construction and projects rehabilitation embarked upon between 2010 and 2018 were not adequate to achieve a reduction in the number of out-of-school children or improve accessibility to education in Osun State.

The classrooms facilities provided would result in wastage with a large number of school-age pupils out of school. Therefore, service delivery function in education has suffered a serious setback, particularly with the insufficient teachers' enrollment at the local government level. The delivery of quality education is a function of adequate trained teachers. The researcher claims that the state lacked the capacity to deliver services in education due to a large number of pupils of school age that had no access to education.

Discussion of Findings

A revenue is an income, especially that of an organization and of a substantial nature. A state's annual income from which public expenses are met. This study aimed to examine the influence of internally generated revenue on the revenue profile of Osun State. The first objective was to examine how IGR influence the finances of Ilesa West Local Government Area of Osun State, Nigeria. The results revealed that State local government joint Account has helped to reduced wasteful spending and corruption in the local government. Also, state local government joint account has resulted in effective monitoring of local government expenditure in South Western Nigeria.

However, state local government joint account has led to reduction in mismanagement and corrupt practices at the local government in the South Western Nigeria. Similarly, the findings showed that disbursement of funds from the state local government joint account is highly efficient and transparent. In a study on the interrelationship between total government expenditure and total tax revenue in Barbados, it was revealed from the empirical findings that a unidirectional causality exists from tax revenue to government expenditure (Banabo, & Koroye, 2015).

The second objective determined the impact of Internal Generated Revenue on the level of infrastructural development of Ilesa West Local Government Areas of Osun State. The study revealed

that service delivery function in education has suffered a serious setback, particularly with the insufficient teachers' enrollment at the local government levels. The delivery of quality education is a function of adequate trained teachers.

Conclusion

There is the need for management and organizational approach that emphasizes services, support and information for the honest tax payers. Increase tax revenue is a function of effective enforcement strategy which is the pure responsibility of tax administrators. Many believe it is the statutory allocations that can make a state perform its civic duties. States that have the 13% derivation allocated to them are considered having the leverage to perform better but this has not been the case. The potentials of some states are hidden within their territories and must be exploited urgently.

It is important to remember that, well targeted public policies, regulations and investments in key sectors can contribute to growth, and this growth will contribute to government revenue. While good governance cannot be over-emphasized, we citizens also need to be aware that there is a need to; Advocate for transparent, evidence-based plans to support economic diversification, hold leaders accountable for implementing those plans with public oversight, transparency and accountability, advocate for high quality public investments and effective service delivery in education, health, transport, power, etc. Advocate for a fair and efficient taxation, and pay taxes as a citizen investing in the future of the country is also paramount.

Recommendations

In view of the above findings, the study, therefore, makes the following recommendations:

1. There should be sufficient fundind by government and non-government organization. Local government should equally diversify, and strengthen her internally generated revenue base through tax, levies, rates and other charges. Avoid using IGR for political patronage.
2. Authority of the various local governments in Nigeria should embark on programme of attitude or value re- orientation for the people of their domain concerning feeling of social or stained isolation and lack of patriotism.
3. The state government should be checked from controlling local government councils on the way they spend the money made available to them.
4. Periodic review on the local government accounts by the external auditors should be emphasized for proper accountability.

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